

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: Fiasorgbor****FIRST NAME: Nutifafa Kodzo****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. Kabiru Gulma**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2010 on Windows 7)

INTRODUCTION TO ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

To carry out research based studies like a doctoral study requires an extensive review of similar works carried out by others. Presentation of these works is a skill required by any person undertaking a doctoral study. Euclid University's doctoral programme is based largely on written communication. There is, therefore, the need for students undertaking doctoral studies in Euclid University to be well versed in the writing of academic essays in order to appreciate and enjoy their studies. This requirement clearly knocks out potential students, including myself, who are not too familiar with the nitty-gritties of academic writing though well qualified to pursue doctoral degree programmes. It is, therefore, relieving to know that the first course in the Euclid University's doctoral programme, ACA-401D introduces and equips the student with the essentials of academic writing so as to enable him/her successfully complete the doctoral programme in good time. The course pack under review is an eighty-three (83)-paged document, which covers the structure, ethics, style and language of academic writing.

2) STRUCTURE OF ACADEMIC PAPER

Academic essays are intended and expected to answer a question and should have a thesis statement and an argument. In attempting to answer the question, relevant literature is to be reviewed and duly acknowledged. This helps to know if similar studies have already been conducted to answer or touched on aspects of the question being asked. Literature review also gives a better understanding and appreciation of the question being answered. After an extensive review of similar works, the writer is expected to identify

the key words and the approach to adopt to tackle the question as well as present the answer in a well-structured manner (EUCLID 2015, 2).

A well-structured academic essay should clearly communicate ideas and answers to the question and should include an introduction, body and conclusion. A brief overview of the essay topic is captured in the introduction. Though brief, the introduction must include the thesis statement and a summary of all the main ideas relating to the question and answers. The discussions leading to answering the essay question are presented in the body and these include one's knowledge, grasp of reviewed materials and answer to the research question. In the conclusion, the writer basically summarizes the main points and it includes a final and broad statement consisting of implications, recommendations and future directions for research among others. The conclusion should be completely devoid of new ideas (EUCLID 2015, 4).

a) Ethics in Academic Writing

As already noted, a good and interesting academic write-up requires extensive review of a number of relevant literature. After this review, one is expected to acknowledge the sources of information gathered using an approved referencing style to avoid plagiarism. Plagiarism is an academic offence and all effort is required to avoid it in an essay. Plagiarism arises when a source of information in a paper is not duly acknowledged (EUCLID 2015, 8-13). The solution to avoiding plagiarism is to properly cite the author or source of the information used in carrying out one's study. The course pack, on page fifteen (15) mentioned two things worthy of note about citing sources of information used in academic writing. These are "in-text citations" and "list of works cited". In-text citation involves citing the piece of work used within the actual text itself. Quotations and paraphrases are usually cited using "in-text citation". Paraphrases are the accurate representation of an author's ideas and information in one's words. Unlike paraphrases, quotations are the exact words of an author and are cited using quotation marks to capture exactly what is being quoted. However, for long quotations, over four lines, the quoted statement should be indented and allowed to stand on its own like a separate paragraph. It is advised that quotations are used only when there is a strong need for it, especially, for emphasis or to persuade a reader (EUCLID 2015, 15-24).

"List of works cited" on the other hand is the list of literature reviewed while writing a paper. It is often found at the end of an academic paper and referred to as bibliography or reference list. It provides more details on each of the sources cited in the paper. These publication details include the authors' name, title of works cited and year of publications among others. Specific referencing styles are preferred by specific institutions or disciplines and these formats are to be used in citing sources such as books, journals and websites among other sources. The course pack highlighted some formats to be used for books including online books and for websites (EUCLID 2015, 33-34).

b) Style and Language in Academic Writing

The style and language used in academic writing is very important in conveying the author's message. For doctoral study at Euclid University, Chicago rules (Turabian) and American English Language are preferred to other internationally recognized rules. Irrespective of the style and language used, Euclid University expects consistency in the use of a selected style and language (EUCLID 2015, 52-53). The course pack highlighted the differences between American and British English, which are both variants of world English. Both American and British English are noted to be more similar than different with notable differences attributed to differences in national histories and cultural development. The course pack further gave examples of the differences between the American and British usages. Among the differences is the placement of punctuations either inside or outside of quotation marks. Punctuation inside of quotation marks is the American style while outside the quotation marks is British. The usage of a particular language is therefore expected to go with its punctuation rules (EUCLID 2015, 54-58).

The course pack further provides a crib sheet which indicates a Turabian revolution in referencing dates in the format: Month, Day, Year and is referred to as the standard American format. Prior to this revolution, dates were presented in the universal or European format: Day, Month, Year (EUCLID 2015, 70).

The course pack also provides a number of Latin expressions and abbreviations. Usage of Latin abbreviations are acceptable and appropriate in footnotes, bibliographies, and informal writing but the use of the English equivalent of the Latin abbreviation is recommended in business, formal and technical writing so as to avoid misinterpretation by target audiences (EUCLID 2015, 78-83).

3) CONCLUSION

As part of my doctoral study in the Euclid University, I reviewed the ACA-401D course pack for period one (1) to equip myself with the skills of academic writing. This was an interesting material as it gave me the basics of academic writing and an idea of what is expected of me as a doctoral student in this University. Highlights were given on the structure of an essay, plagiarism, citing reviewed works and referencing. The course pack also shed some light on the choice of writing style and language to be used in writing academic essays. Though the Chicago Style (Turabian) and American English were recommended due to their universal appeal, the university accepts other internationally recognized styles but insists on consistency in the use of any selected style and language.

My part of the world, specifically, Ghana, mainly associates with the European format of dates and British English due to the influence of its colonial masters, specifically, Britain. I have therefore used the European date format and British English Language throughout my education up to the master's level and more inclined toward using these formats for my doctoral study. However, due to the similarities between the

two languages, I anticipate difficulty in ensuring consistency in the use of the British English but I will endeavour to study these differences so as to pursue the doctoral programme at the Euclid University with ease.

REFERENCES

EUCLID University. 2015. *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 1*. Retrieved from: <http://www.eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-1/>

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.